

Leadership, Employee Empowerment, Organizational Commitment, and Employee Performance in Senior High School

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ABSTRACT

Research about leadership on employee performance within an organization is something of interest to be discussed at this time. This study about the influence of leadership on employee performance through employee empowerment and organizational commitment at the Senior High School level in the Petra Christian School Board (PPPK Petra). This research was conducted in all of teachers at the Senior High School in the Petra Christian School Board against 103 peoples who already have a Educator Certificate. Measurement of leadership variable used eight indicators; variable employee performance used eight indicators; employee empowerment variable used twelve indicators; and organizational commitment variables used six indicators that have been tested for reliability and validity. The results showed direct effect of leadership on employee performance, and there is indirect effect of leadership on employee performance through employee empowerment and organizational commitment as an intervening variable, so the total effect of the leadership on employee performance stronger.

Keywords : Leadership; Employee Empowerment; Organizational Commitment; Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Background

Leadership is one of the important factors in an organization because of the success or failure of an organization is determined by the leader. Leadership is defined as the process of influence others to support the achievement of organizational goals relevan. Leadership also defined as the ability to influence a group toward the achievement of targets, where resources of this influence is formal (Robbins, 2007, p. 432). Leadership is also called as the ability to influence a group toward the achievement of a vision or set goals (Robbins and Judge, 2015, p. 249). the style of leadership that made a leader in influencing subordinates are different. The style of leadership is seen as a combination of traits, characteristics, skills and behaviors leaders use when interacting with their subordinates (Jeremy, Coetzee, and Cilliers, 2012).

In modern leadership theory there are five styles of leadership: charismatic leadership, transactional leadership, transformational leadership, visionary leadership, and culture-based leadership (Bass, 1990 and Yukl, 1994). The transactional leadership style focuses more on leadership-subordinate relationship without any effort to create change for subordinates.

One way that is done by a company or organization to face globalization and the competition is doing or empowerment the employee (Celik, Iraz, Cakici, and Celik, 2014). Empowerment is related to how to manage employees in order to do their job properly in an organization or company (Celik et al., 2014); (Ivancevich, Konopaske, and Matteson, 2007). Employee empowerment is also a role for employees to help employees to feel that their contribution to the company or organization has the meaning (Goudarzvandchegini and Kheradmand, 2013). Empowering employees to work for the organization to be able to retain its employees who have the qualities, skills, knowledge and abilities and hire more staff, efficient and effective manner (Mehbarani and Shajari, 2013; Jafari et al., 2013).

Organizational commitment is one of the key objectives in maintaining and developing an organization. Loyalty of an employee against his employer needs to be tested by considering factors of organizational commitment (Meyer, 1997). Organizational commitment indicates the emotional impact of an employee who is directly related to and inherent in an organization (Aghazadeh, Keimasi, and Alaei, 2013).

Performance is the result of a work that has been done (Folorunso, Adewale, and Abodunde, 2014). This performance illustrates the level of achievement of setiappekerjaan and regulatory compliance organization, expectations, or the need for the role of employees. Job performance is defined as well as the achievement of the results of any action by the expertise of every employee doing so in some situations. More than that, work performances is also a productivity stating the quantity, quality and contribute to the work (Folorunso et al., 2014).

Research on the analysis of leadership, employee empowerment, organizational commitment, and employee performance in Petra Christian Senior High School's perception done on teachers. Teachers as the main focus as the human resources in the education organization certainly has a very important role for the sustainability of the organization. Through competency standards and the implementation of Teachers Certification by the Department of Education as one of the empowerment process expected to be an improvement of the life that is more just, democratic among teachers and education personnel. However, the empowerment of the Petra Christian Senior High School's teachers through the program Teachers Certification organized by the Ministry of National Education is not automatically able to increase the commitment of teachers to the educational organization where she worked that ultimately have an impact on employee performance.

THEORY AND HYPHOTESIS

Leadership and employee performance

Leadership is very important to achieve organizational goals. Since leadership is regarded as a key factor for improving the performance of the organization, stated that the success or failure of an organization depends on the effectiveness of leadership at all levels. Many researchers of the study stated that leadership can affect the attitudes, beliefs, and the ability of employees to achieve organizational goals (Shafie, Baghersalimi, and Barghi, 2013). One of them is the transformational leadership style was known as one of effective leadership style that has four dimensions that influence ideals, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. The leadership styles provide high performance and provide a major influence on job satisfaction (Shafie et al., 2013). In this study, leadership includes transactional and transformational leadership style. The hypotheses for this study are.

H1: There is the influence of leadership on employee performance

Leadership and employee empowerment

Organization that emphasizes the importance of employee empowerment will motivate and retain the employees they have. This will impact on job satisfaction, employee performance and productivity (Murari, 2013). In the free market economy, empower employees needed to improve innovation, quality products and services to address challenges globally competition. In other words, the employee strength through empowerment can enhance the competitive advantage of a company. Leadership style is an important thing for the success of the organization. Each type of leadership style gives a special impact on the empowerment of employees. The study revealed that there is a relationship between transformational leadership and transactional leadership style and the empowerment of employees (Men and Stacks, 2013). Both of these leadership styles to positively affect employees in terms of feelings to control. In other words, empowerment under taken by the leadership of a strong impact on employees. Greater transactional leadership style in engaging employees to give authority to the decision-making compared to transactional leadership style (Men and Stacks, 2013). However, other studies found that both styles are both transactional and transformational kepemimpinan not have a significant relationship to psychology empowerment of employees that include competence and self-efficacy (Men and Stacks, 2013). It depends on a number of factors in which an individual basis depending on the research variables do. In this study, leadership (leadership) includes transactional and transformational leadership style. The hypo theses for this study are.

H2: There is the influence of leadership on employee empowerment.

Leadership and organizational commitment

Employee performance cannot be separated from the role of leadership. A leader has the duty and responsibility to encourage employees or employees achieve optimal performance. To achieve this, the leader demanded to know the members of his organization as a whole so as to foster harmonious cooperation among the components of the organization to achieve organizational success. One indicator of the success is the component of organizational commitment of subordinates (Raharjo and Nafisa, 2006). The existence of a leader in influencing the organizational commitment of subordinates is also supported by research Lai, Lune, Chai, and Ling, (2014) in Malaysia, which measures the principal's leadership style influence on organizational commitment of teachers on school performance. The study found that the principal's leadership style transformational yielded significant results positively influence the affective commitment and continuance commitment. While the influence of the principal's leadership with transformational leadership style did not yield significant results. Research conducted by Lai, Luen, Chai, and Ling, (2014) also found that the principal's leadership style transactional yielded significant results to organizational commitment of teachers only on affective commitment only. The influence of school leadership on transactional leadership style does not significantly affect continuance commitment and normative commitment of teachers in Malaysia as respondents in the study. Principal with the transformational leadership style significantly affect on organizational commitment of teachers are also found in the study by Yu, Leithwood, and Jantzi, (2002), in Hong Kong. The commitment of the teachers in this study is the center of the reform or reform of school organization (Yu, Leithwood, and Jantzi, 2002). The existence of a leader at school that can affect the commitment of the teachers to make changes in schools is indispensable. Other researchers such as Avolio (1999) and Bass (1998) also found that the leadership in an organization with transformational leadership style tends to provide a greater influence on the level of commitment of its followers when compared to transactional leadership style and laissez faire leadership style. (Lai, Lune, Chai, and Ling, 2014). The hypotheses for this study are:

H3: There is the influence of leadership on organizational commitment

Employee Empowerment on Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment called as well as an individual attachment, loyalty and identification with the organization (Meyer and Allen, 1984). Empowerment may contribute to the feeling of commitment to the organization through the process of mutual relations (Liden et al., 2000). Employees tend to appreciate the organization that provides the opportunity to give freedom in decision-making, face challenges, and responsible as well as the feel of the meaning, impact, self-determination, and feel the results of the condition. It is reciprocal. If empowerment is done properly, it can increase employee commitment will be the identification, engagement and loyalty to the organization (Liden et al., 2000). Ambad and Bahron, (2012) in his research also found relation between empowerment and organizational commitment in the construction sector in Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia. Two dimensions of employee empowerment, namely self-determination and the impact has a positive relationship with organizational commitment. While the other two dimensions of employee empowerment, ie meaning and competence do not indicate a positive relationship with organizational commitment. The discovery indicates that employees in the construction sector feel their empowerment through the provision of autonomy, freedom and opportunity to them to determine how they do their job. In the end the employee more committed to their organizations and put the best effort that ensures durability organization (Ambad and Bahron, 2012). Results of research conducted by Pratiwi (2012) showed that there is a direct effect of empowerment and organizational commitment. Employees who have an internal locus of control is high, usually have greater expectations on certain tasks. In other words, employees are empowered to have a sense (meaning) is to believe that they have an influence on employees and organizational units aspirational against him. Thus it can be said that through empowerment, employees will have a strong personal control on how to do the job and have confidence in his ability (self-efficacy). So that, empowered employees will have a sense of responsibilities on their work and a sense of responsibility for the organization as part of the organization's commitment. In this study, employee empowerment includes dimensions meaningfulness, competence, self-determination, and impact. The hypotheses for this study are:

H 4: There is the influence organization commitment to employee empowerment

Empowerment and Employee Performance

Thomas and Velthouse (1990) defines empowerment is a need for individual freedom to act and at the same time responsible for his actions in accordance with the employee's job duties (Lestari and Yuniarto, 2015). Empowerment is a matter that cannot be avoided for employees to provide fast service to customers in the event of a fault corrective action to save the customer's time is very valuable. If in the above case there is a delay to the fault corrective action, it can cause the organization to lose a lot of customers (Jafari et al., 2013). Through the empowerment of employees expected to work can be done more effectively and efficiently than when the non-enforcement of employee empowerment (Jafari et al., 2013). Organizations need people who are empowered are able to innovate and improve product and service quality to customers (Babak and Alizadeh, 2014). The act of empowerment to help members of the organization so that the employees or the organization have confidence that they are able to do a good performance, and it is offset by the growing relationship between the work and performance to bring the cultural contribution of the work (Ivancevich et al., 2007, p. 86). in this study, employee empowerment includes dimensions meaningfulness, competence, self-determination, and impact. The hypotheses for this study are:

H5: There is the influence of organizational commitment to employee empowerment

Organizational commitment and employee performance

The existence of organizational commitment of employees can be used by employees to support the organization and maximize the benefits that they gain from the employee's performance. It can occur because of high productivity with the individual performance of each employee looks balanced (Osa and Amos, 2014). Previous research shows a connection between the dimensions of organizational commitment to employee performance. For example Negin, Omid, and Ahmad, (2013) investigated the influence of organizational commitment on job performance among staff Malik bank. The results found that the dimensions of organizational commitment that affective commitment, normative and kontinuen positive and significant effect on job performance. Other researchers are Qaisar et al., (2012) also found the effect of organizational dimensions that affective commitment, normative and kontinuen the performance of employees in the police station of Pakistan (Folorunso et al., 2014). According to Chen and Francesco, (2003), organizational commitment is the subject of research that shows there is a significant effect on employee performance and employee turnover. Researcher Chen and Francesco (2003) also found in studies conducted that there is a relationship between organizational commitment and performance of the 253 pairs -subordinate supervisor in the field of pharmaceutical company in South China. The study found a significant relationship to the affective component of commitment on organizational commitment affect the performance compared to other commitments (Wong, 2014). In this study, the organization's commitment includes three dimensions namely affective commitment, kontinuen commitment, and normative commitment. The hypotheses for this study are:

H 6: There is the influence of organizational commitment on employ performance.

Picture 1: Research Model

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Population and Sample

The population in this study consist of all teachers in the Senior High School at the Petra Christian Christian School Board, such us : 71 people from Petra 1 Christian Senior High School, 65 people from Petra 2 Christian Senior High School, 27 people from Petra 3 Christian Senior High School, 30 people from Petra 4 Christian Senior High School, and

47 people from Petra 5 Christian Senior High School with the total numbers of all teachers at the Senior High School in the Petra Christian School Board are 240 peoples. The samples in this study are all teachers at the Senior High School level in the Petra Christian School Board already have a Certificate of Educator numbering 103 people.

Data's Analysis

Sampling of all Senior High School teachers in Petra Christian School Board who have obtained certificates from the Ministry of Education which amounted to 103 people using a questionnaire. The results of the questionnaire was measured using a Likert scale with ratings scale ranges from 1 to 5, with the following criteria: 1 = strongly disagree; 2 = disagree; 3 = disagree; 4 = agree; 5 = strongly agree. Leadership variables measure with eight indicators includes characteristics transactional leadership and transformational leadership according Luthans (2008). Employee performance variables measured using the criteria of performance according to Gomes (2001), which consists of eight indicators. Employee empowerment variables measured using indicators meaningfulness (Liden et al., 2000), competence (Liden et al., 2000), self-determination (Spreitzer et al., 1997), and impact (Liden et al., 2000) consists of twelve indicators. Organizational commitment variables measured using indicators affective commitment, continuence commitment, and normative commitment (Luthans 2008 and Sersic, 1999) which consists of six indicators.

Data are analyzed using SPSS version 22.0 to descriptive analysis and Structural Equation Model (SEM) using PLS Smart program. Descriptive analysis explains the validity and reliability of test results, the profile of respondents, and the answer of respondents about the influence of leadership, employee empowerment, organizational commitment on employee performance. Analysis of Partial Least Square (PLS) is use to test the research hypothesis. Significance test with a significant criterion when p values <0.05. Structural Equation Model (SEM) has a goodness-of-fit if approached Q-square one. The study hypothesis is declared acceptable when the p-value <0.05. The influence between the variables seen by the direct effect and indirect effect. The direct effect is measure by the effect of leadership on employee performance, while the indirect effect is measure by the effect of leadership on employee performance through employee empowerment and organizational commitment as intervening variable.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Of the 103 teachers at the Senior High School level in the Petra Christian School Board as the samples of this study consists of 69 women (67%) and 34 men (33%). The age of respondents at most at the age of 46 to 55 years with the number of 62 people (60.2%) . A total of 90 people (87.4%) are married and 13 people (12.6%) unmarried. Experience teaches respondents ranged from 11 to 25 years as many as 72 people (95.1%). Class rank of respondents varies from IIIA to IV B and class rank is the highest number IIIB were 33 people (32%). Education levels of respondents to the levels of S-1 are 81 people (79.6%) and S-2 are 21 people (20.4%). The numbers of Senior High School teachers in the Petra Christian School Board are: SMA Kristen Petra 1 consist of 29 people , SMA Kristen Petra 2 consist of 26 people , SMA Kristen Petra 3 consist of 17 people, SMA Kristen Petra 5 consist of 16 people , and SMA Kristen Petra 4 consist of 15 people. Position of respondents consist of Principal, Vice Principal, Guardian Class and subject teachers. All respondents already have Educator Certificate from the Ministry of National Education with the highest number on the receipt of the Educator Certificate in 2009 as many as 25 people (24.3%). Distance to the respondent's house to work locations vary, while the distance respondent's from the house to the work place are 0 to 5 km as many as 28 people (27.2%).

To test the hypothesis of the research in this study use analysis Partial Least Square (PLS). Here is a picture of PLS Models is tested:

Picture-2: PLS Model

Based on **Figure-2**, outer model testing convergent validity, discriminant validity and composite reliability, is known that the loading factor of each indicator research > 0.5 , so that each indicator in this study is said to meet the convergent validity for further analysis. That in general the value of loading factor $> 0,7$. This result shows overall indicators are reliable and can be use for further analysis. To determine the discriminant validity in research variables can be done by comparing the value of the AVE's root each variable with correlation between variables. **Table-1** is a presentation of data related to the AVE's value, AVE's roots as well as the correlation between variables:

Table-1 AVE, AVE Roots, and Correlation Between Variables						
Variable	AVE	AVE Roots	Leadership	Employee Empowerment	Organizational Commitment	Employee Performance
Leadership	0,507	0,712	1,000	0,634	0,540	0,621
Employee Empowerment	0,502	0,708		1,000	0,442	0,409
Organizational Commitment	0,551	0,742			1,000	0,435
Employee Performance	0,738	0,859				1,000

AVE's value all variables > 0.5 . This study also notes that all the correlation value is smaller than the value of the AVE's root. Based on these results it can be stated that any variables use in this research model, already have good discriminate validity. To test the reliability values of indicators at a variable can be known from the value of composite reliability. A variable can be declared fulfilling composite reliability if the composite reliability's value > 0.7 . **Table 3** below show the composite reliability's value of each variable use in this study:

Table-2 Composite Reliability	
Variable	Composite Reliability
Leadership	0,891
Employee Empowerment	0,922
Organizational Commitment	0,879
Employee Performance	0,958

Composite reliability's value of all the variables > 0.7 , these results indicate that each variable use in this research model has met the composite reliability so that it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability internal consistency. The evaluation path confident use to show how strong the effect or influence of independent variables to the dependent variable. **Table 3** below show the path coefficient value of the research results. To test the hypothesis in this study is done by looking at the t value and p-value.

Table-3 Path Coefficient				
Correlation Effect	Original Sample	Standar Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
X -> Y	0,249	0,100	2,491	0,013
X -> Z1	0,634	0,063	10,092	0,000
X -> Z2	0,260	0,095	2,722	0,007
Z1 -> Y	0,217	0,097	2,239	0,026
Z1 -> Z2	0,442	0,084	5,283	0,000
Z2 -> Y	0,435	0,116	3,748	0,000

Table-3 show that all hypothesis in this study been accepted. Based on the data processing done by researchers using SmartPLS program, the value of R-Square as follows:

Table 4 R-Square Value's	
Variable	Value's
Employee Empowerment	0,402
Organizational Commitment	0,408
Employee Performance	0,598

Based on data in **table 4**, shows that the value of R-Square for employee empowerment is 0.402. This value explains that employee empowerment influenced by the leadership of 40.2%. The value of R-Square for the organizational commitment is 0.408. This result explains that organizational commitments are influenced by leadership and employee empowerment about 40.8%. Furthermore, to the value of R- Square for employee performance are 0.598. This result explains that employee performance can be explained by the leadership, employee empowerment, and organizational commitment numbers 59.8%.

The goodness of fit of research model's indicated by the value of the Q-Square and it has the same meaning as the coefficient of determination (R-Square) in the regression analysis. The higher of the Q-Square, indicates that the model can be more fit to the data. The calculation results of Q-Square values from the model as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Q-Square} &= 1 - [(1-0,402) \times (1-0,408) \times (1-0,598)] \\ &= 0,857686 \end{aligned}$$

Based on Q-square value, it can be shown that the prediction ability of employee performance from leadership, employee empowerment, and organizational commitment is 86%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the research model for this study has a goodness of fit. The influence of the direct effect and indirect effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable from the model, shown in table 5.

Table 5 Direct Effects and Indirect Effects of Leadership on Employee Performance	
Variable	Path Coefficient
Direct Effects:	
Leadership to Employee Performance	0,249
Indirect Effects:	
Leadership to Employee empowerment to Employee performance (0,634 x 0,217 = 0,138)	0,138
Leadership to Organizational commitment to Employee performance (0,260 x 0,435 = 0,113)	0,113
Leadership to Employee empowerment to Organizational commitment to Employee performance (0,634 x 0,442 x 0,435 = 0,122)	0,122
Total	0,622

Based on information from table 5, it seen the direct effect on employee performance by leadership is greater than the indirect effect of leadership on employee performance through employee empowerment and organizational commitment. The indirect effect of leadership on employee performance through employee empowerment and organizational commitment as an intervening variable can amplify the total effect of leadership on employee performance, so that the total effect of leadership on employee performance even stronger.

CONCLUSIONS AND UGGESTIONS

Conclusions

1. There is a direct effect of leadership on employee performance in the Christian Senior High School in the Petra Christian School Board. Based on the result of this study found that the most dominant leadership style applied was transactional leadership.
2. There is an indirect effect of leadership on employee performance through employee empowerment and organizational commitment as intervening variable.
3. The indirect effect of leadership on employee performance through employee empowerment and organizational commitment as an intervening variable can amplify the total effect of leadership on employee performance, so that the total effect of leadership on employee performance even stronger.

Suggestions

1. The results of this study can be develop at all levels of schooling in Petra Christian School Board both on teachers already have a certified or not.
2. The research model can be used for research in other schools outside of the Petra Christian School Board.
3. To obtain the Q-square higher further research needs to be done by adding another variable.

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